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***Corresponding Author:**
Rohit,
Student, Department of
Electrical and Electronics
Engineering, PDA College
of Engineering, Kalaburagi,
Karnataka, India

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AI Voice Assistant Device Using IoT

**Mohammed Farhan¹, Rohit^{2*}, Sanjeev Kumar R A³,
Megha Upase⁴**

^{1,2}Student, Department of Electrical and Electronics
Engineering, PDA College of Engineering, Kalaburagi,
Karnataka, India

^{3,4}Assistant Professor, Department of Electrical and
Electronics Engineering, PDA College of Engineering,
Kalaburagi, Karnataka, India

ABSTRACT

The rapid advancement of Artificial Intelligence (AI) and the Internet of Things (IoT) has enabled the development of intelligent systems capable of human-like communication and between humans and machines through cloud-based APIs, including Google Speech-to-Text (STT), Google Text-to-Speech (TTS), and OpenAI (ChatGPT). The assistant processes user commands, generates intelligent responses, and controls IoT devices via ThingESP integration, while Twilio is used for automated alerts and communication. The device features an I2S-based audio interface for high-quality voice input and output, and operates on rechargeable power for portability. This system demonstrates how low-cost embedded hardware can be transformed into an intelligent assistant capable of real-time speech interaction, smart control, and cloud communication. The results highlight the system's scalability and potential for applications in smart homes, education, healthcare, and personal assistance.

Keywords:- AI Voice Assistant, ESP32, IoT, Google STT, Google TTS, OpenAI API, ChatGPT, ThingESP, Twilio, I2S Audio Module, Smart Automation, Speech Recognition, Text-to- Speech

INTRODUCTION

Artificial Intelligence (AI) has revolutionized human computer interaction by enabling devices to understand and respond to natural speech. Voice assistants such as Alexa, Siri, and Google Assistant have popularized conversational AI; however, these systems are primarily cloud-dependent and operate on high-end hardware. The proposed AI Voice Assistant Using IoT aims to provide similar capabilities on a low-cost embedded platform using the ESP32 microcontroller.

The system listens to user speech through an I2S microphone, converts it to text using Google Speech-to-Text (STT), and processes the query using OpenAI's ChatGPT API for intelligent responses. The response is then converted back into audio using Google Text-to-Speech (TTS) and played through a speaker. Beyond communication, the system can control IoT devices through Thing ESP and send emergency alerts using Twilio APIs control.

This paper focuses the design and implementation of an AI Voice Assistant Using IoT, built on the ESP32 microcontroller platform. The proposed system enables natural voice interaction. By integrating AI and IoT, the project bridges the gap between embedded systems and intelligent automation. It provides a portable, interactive, and cost-effective solution for speech-based control and information access, suitable for smart homes, educational tools, and assistive technologies.

RELATED WORKS

Several researchers and developers have explored the integration of Artificial Intelligence (AI) and Internet of Things (IoT) to create intelligent voice-controlled systems. Various commercial voice assistants such as Amazon Alexa, Google

Assistant, and Apple Siri have already demonstrated the potential of combining voice recognition with cloud-based AI services for seamless human machine interaction. However, these systems are also dependent on proprietary hardware and closed ecosystems.

In recent academic studies, low-cost microcontrollers like ESP8266 and ESP32 have been widely used to implement custom voice-controlled IoT projects. For instance, some works focused on home automation systems that respond to voice commands using local speech recognition modules. Others implemented speech-to-text conversion using Google STT API and text-to-speech synthesis using Google TTS to provide interactive feedback.

Previous projects have also utilized ThingESP and Blynk platforms for IoT control and Twilio for sending SMS or email notifications. While these systems achieved partial automation, they lacked intelligent text understanding and natural conversation abilities.

The proposed AI Voice Assistant Device Using IoT advances these earlier designs by integrating OpenAI (ChatGPT) for intelligent response generation, creating a system capable of both smart communication and automated IoT control. This makes it more adaptable, conversational, and intelligent compared to traditional command-based assistants.

S. S. Vigneshwar and K. L. Kumar, "AI Voice assistant Using Python and API," in Proc. 2024 Int. Conf. on Advances in Data Engineering and Intelligent Computing Systems (ADICS), 2024, DOI:10.1109/ADICS58448.2024.10533536. This paper proposes the development of a voice assistant integrated into an augmented reality (AI) environment. Voice assistants have become

increasingly popular in recent years, with the widespread adoption of smart speakers and mobile devices. Meanwhile, AI technology has also advanced rapidly, offering new ways to interact with digital information and objects in the real world. The proposed system aims to combine the convenience and ease of use of a voice assistant with the immersive and interactive nature of AI.

The user will be able to access the voice assistant through a wearable device, such as smart glasses or a headset. The voice assistant will respond to the user's voice commands and provide relevant information and assistance, displayed as virtual overlays in the AI environment. The implementation of the system will require overcoming technical challenges related to the integration of voice recognition and AI technology, as well as ensuring user privacy and security. However, the potential benefits of a voice assistant in any environment make it a promising area for future research and development.

M. Subi, M. Rajeswari, J. J. Rajan, and S. Harshini, "AI Based Desktop Viz: A Voice Activated Personal Assistant Futuristic and Sustainable Technology," In Proc. 2024 10th Int. Conf. On Communication and Signal Processing (ICCSP), 2024, doi: 10.1109/ICCSP60870.2024.10543665.

Modern technology has led to the development of advanced technologies that employ a variety of cutting-edge techniques, including speech recognition, machine learning, artificial intelligence, and OpenAI.

A popular example of these technologies is Voice-Activated personal assistant this is one of the most often used examples of speech recognition and machine learning technologies. Using Open AI, these

models may be adjusted and their exploratory potential can be enhanced. This AI- powered desktop has been configured to pull data that the user requests using OpenAI. Additionally, it makes use of the Auto GUI package in Python to control the mouse and click on windows in other programs.

While the existing model used a standard user interface to present the user with stored outputs, this model makes use of OpenAI to deliver more precise and comprehensive results. Furthermore, Auto GUI facilitates automatic user window interaction. This model is an excellent illustration of OpenAI, GUI, and speech recognition combined

R. Bolimera, K. P. Kumar, R. Sunkuru, P. Mahesh, and M. Pekkamwar, "AI Enabled Voice Assistant For Visually Impaired," In Proc. 2024 15th Int. Conf. On Computing Communication and Networking Technologies (ICCCNT), 2024, doi: 10.1109/ICCCNT61001.2024.10724542.

In today's world, everyone benefits from smart assistants, which allow us to speak with intelligent aides and ask robotic questions. The majority of people on the planet are pulled to technology in many different ways, whether it be through desktop computers, laptops, cell-phones, etc. It is a speech-recognition intelligent smart assistant that takes text or voice input from the user, processes it, and outputs the results in a number of ways, including speaking the user's search results.

A few instances of intelligent assistants are Alexa, Siri, and Google Assistant. They still have issues with human connection, and they are unable to recognize voices. In addition to requiring internet and Wi-Fi access in order to interact with users, those Google

Assistant issues also have a very narrow language set, which can cause a lot of difficulties for users. One feature of Android cell-phones is Google Assistant. Nevertheless, in order for this application to work, an Internet connection is necessary.

Nevertheless, our suggested solution is also capable of operating without an Internet connection. In order to solve the problem and implement multiple languages, we are using a Raspberry Pi. On the Pi, data in multiple languages is loaded and stored, enabling the user to access any

R. Jampala, M. Bhavanam, D. S. Kola, I. R. Pannerselvam, and A. N. Gummadi, "The Evolution Of Voice Assistants: From Text-To-Speech To Conversational Ai," in Proc. 2024 2nd Int. Conf. on Intelligent Data Communication Technologies and Internet of Things (IDCIOT), 2024, doi: 10.1109/IDCIOT59759.2024.10467739.

Voice assistants have undergone a remarkable transformation, evolving from simple text-to-speech systems to sophisticated conversational AI platforms. This exploration delves into the trajectory of this evolution, tracing the technological advancements and pivotal milestones that have propelled voice assistants into the realm of natural language understanding and human-like interaction.

Beginning with the rudimentary text-to-speech functionalities, the narrative progresses through the integration of machine learning and neural networks, enabling voice assistants to comprehend context, nuances, and intent.

The shift towards conversational AI marks a significant turning point, where these assistants have transcended mere

command-following tools to become intuitive, adaptive, and capable of holding meaningful dialogues. This abstract encapsulates the journey of voice assistants, highlighting the pivotal technologies and breakthroughs that have shaped their evolution, ultimately leading to the dawn of conversational AI.

P. Kunekar, A. Deshmukh, A. Bichare, and K. Gunjal, "AI BASED DESKTOP VOICE ASSISTANT," in Proc. 2023 5th Int. Conf. on Nascent Technologies in Engineering (ICNTE), 2023, doi: 10.1109/ICNTE56631.2023.10146699.

From the past few years, Artificial Intelligence (AI) has shown remarkable progress, and its future is growing day by day. Natural Language Processing (NLP) is an application of AI. A voice assistant utilizes cloud computing to integrate AI and communicate with users in natural language. In households today, millions of devices use voice assistants due to their ease of use. Universities and schools are just starting to use smart speakers with voice assistants.

Voice assistants are the greatest innovation in AI that can change people's lives in a significant way. Initially, voice assistants were introduced on smartphones, then they became popular. The idea was widely accepted by all. A voice assistant was initially used in smartphones and laptops, but now it is also found in home automation systems and smart speakers.

As devices become smarter, they are interfacing with humans in a language that is easier to understand. Programs based upon desktop voice assistants recognize and respond to human voices via an integrated voice system. We will discuss the main problems and limitations of voice assistants in this paper.

Summary: As facial recognition technology advances, ethical considerations have come to the forefront. This section explores the work of ethicists, privacy advocates, and legal scholars who have contributed to discussions on data protection, bias mitigation, and consent within facial recognition systems.

The Issue: The collection, storage, and use of facial data raise significant privacy concerns. Users may not be fully aware of how their facial data is being used and stored. Overall, the literature suggests that ARVA has significant potential in various domains, including retail, education, and hospitality. However, technical challenges, user adoption, and privacy concerns need to be addressed for successful implementation

EXISTING SYSTEM

In the current scenario, most voice assistant systems are built around powerful computers or cloud-connected devices such as smartphones, smart speakers, and PCs. These systems typically rely on high-level programming environments (like Python) and strong internet connectivity to access cloud-based AI models and services. A typical existing voice assistant setup works as follows:

1) Speech Recognition: Use a speech recognition library like Speech Recognition in Python. Recognize the user's voice input to understand commands. Libraries like Speech Recognition with engines such as Google Speech API or other cloud STT services. In some offline setups, local engines like Vosk or CMU Sphinx are used, but these need more processing power than a small microcontroller.

2) Text-to-Speech (TTS): To respond back to the user, existing systems

convert text into audible speech using the Python libraries like pyttsx3 (offline, system TTS) or gTTS (Google Text-to-Speech, online). And many consumer devices (Alexa, Google Assistant, Siri) rely on proprietary, cloud-based TTS engines for natural-sounding voices.

3) Natural Language Processing (NLP): On PCs and servers, Python-based assistants often use NLP libraries like nltk, spaCy, or transformer-based models to understand user intent. And Perform tasks such as intent classification, entity extraction, and context handling, usually with the help of cloud AI services or locally hosted models on a powerful machine.

4) Rule-Based Command Handling: A basic voice assistant in existing systems usually maps recognized text to predefined commands using if-else blocks, dictionaries, or simple intent-matching logic and Executes system-level actions (open an application, play music, search the web, tell time, etc.) directly on the PC or phone.

5) Cloud API Integration: To extend capabilities, most assistants integrate multiple web APIs, for example; Weather APIs for weather reports. And News APIs for headlines. And also Calendar, email, or messaging APIs for reminders and notifications. These systems assume stable internet connectivity and sufficient security to handle API keys and tokens.

6) Dialogue Management on High-Level Platforms: Many existing systems manage conversation flow using the simple state machines or context variables stored in memory. And dedicated dialogue frameworks or cloud services (e.g., Dialog flow, Rasa, or custom chatbot backends) to handle

multi-turn conversations and maintain context.

7) Wake Word Detection on Powerful Devices: Activation is typically done using a wake word such as “Hey Google,” “Alexa,” or “Hey Siri”. On PCs or Raspberry Pi-class devices, libraries or engines like Snow boy (now deprecated), Porcupine, or custom models are used. On commercial devices, wake word detection is often implemented with optimized DSP pipelines and proprietary models, running continuously and consuming more power than a small embedded board usually can afford.

8) Hardware and Deployment Environment: Existing DIY voice assistant systems are usually implemented on laptops, desktops, or Raspberry Pi-class SBCs where Python and full OS support are available. And

some Depend heavily on a reliable internet connection and relatively high RAM/CPU compared to a microcontroller like the ESP32.

PROPOSED SYSTEM

The proposed system, titled “AI Voice Assistant Using API,” introduces an intelligent, real-time voice-driven solution capable of understanding user commands, processing information, and controlling connected devices through a combination of local communication and API-based cloud intelligence.

Unlike traditional computer-based voice assistants, this system is built on a low-power ESP32 platform, equipped with a microphone, speaker, and wireless communication modules, enabling a compact, cost-effective, and always-available voice assistant.

Fig.1:-System Architecture of the Proposed AI Voice

The system is designed to allow users to interact naturally using spoken commands. The assistant continuously listens for a predefined wake word, after which it records the user's speech and interprets the input through API-based processing. The recognized text is then classified into categories such as device commands, announcements, alerts, room-status queries, or general AI queries. For any informational or conversational request, the system communicates with cloud-based APIs such as OpenAI's natural language model to generate concise, context-aware responses.

The proposed system also integrates with external messaging services. Using APIs such as Twilio WhatsApp, the assistant can receive text messages, identify instruction types, and respond accordingly. Messages beginning with keywords like "alert," "announcement," or "message" are played aloud directly by the assistant, while all other text messages follow the same processing pipeline as voice commands. This hybrid interface ensures seamless interaction even when voice input is not practical, such as noisy environments or remote access scenarios.

For physical control and real-time monitoring, the assistant communicates with a remote ESP32-based smart device using secure ESP-NOW communication.

This device controls appliances such as fans and lamps while monitoring environmental parameters like temperature, humidity, and gas levels. Commands issued via voice or WhatsApp are transmitted wirelessly to the smart node, which executes the required action and sends acknowledgements or sensor data back to the main assistant. This distributed architecture ensures reliable operation even with unstable internet, while still benefiting from cloud intelligence when online.

A user-friendly feedback mechanism is implemented through the onboard RGB LED, which represents different system states power-on, Wi-Fi connection, internet access, listening, processing, or idle. This creates a clear visual indicator of the assistant's status at any moment, enhancing user experience during operation.

SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE

The proposed AI Voice Assistant Using API is built around a modular and distributed architecture designed to provide seamless voice interaction, intelligent processing, and real-time device control. The system integrates embedded hardware, wireless communication cloud-based AI services, and local automation to deliver an efficient and responsive assistant.

Fig.2:-System Model

The architecture begins with Voice Input, where the user interacts with the system through an I2S microphone connected to the ESP32-S3. This raw audio signal forms the foundation of all subsequent processing. The input is then passed to the Speech Recognition (STT) Module, which converts the spoken audio into text. Depending on system configuration and network conditions, this conversion may utilize either local processing components or API-based cloud speech-to-text services.

Once text is obtained from the user's speech, it is forwarded to the Command Processing and Interpretation Unit. This stage includes lightweight Natural Language Understanding (NLU) running on the ESP32-S3, responsible for identifying whether the input is a device command, a request for room status, an announcement, a WhatsApp message trigger, or an AI knowledge query. By interpreting keywords and sentence structures, the assistant understands user intent with clarity.

For general knowledge queries or complex responses, the interpreted text is sent through the API Integration Layer, which communicates with external AI services such as OpenAI. This allows the system to access advanced language understanding

and generation capabilities beyond the limitations of local processing. The cloud API returns a text-based response, ensuring accuracy, context-awareness, and natural language quality.

Description of Software and Hardware for Implementation and Testing Plan of the Proposed System

The proposed AI Voice Assistant Using API is implemented using a carefully integrated combination of software and hardware components, each tested thoroughly to ensure reliability, accuracy, and seamless operation. System testing plays a critical role in validating that the complete solution meets all functional and non-functional requirements outlined in the Software Requirement Specification (SRS).

After individual modules undergo unit testing, integration testing is conducted to verify interactions between the speech-processing units, network modules, API communication layers, and device control logic. Once integration is complete, full system testing is performed to evaluate the assistant's real-world behavior, including voice recognition accuracy, response generation, API communication, and smart device control.

On the software side, the system is developed using the Arduino IDE with the ESP32 framework, providing a stable environment for building firmware, debugging, and managing essential libraries such as WiFi, HTTP Client, ArduinoJson, and ESP-NOW. Cloud intelligence is enabled through the OpenAI API, which processes user queries and generates natural-language responses, tested for secure HTTPS communication, token handling, response parsing, and latency performance.

Local automation is managed through ESP-NOW, enabling low-latency peer-to-peer communication between the main ESP32-S3 assistant and the secondary ESP32 smart device. The audio pipeline is supported by the I2S microphone interface for capturing user speech and an I2S amplifier for generating audio responses, both tested for clarity, consistency, and operational robustness.

WhatsApp messaging integration (via APIs such as Twilio) allows text-based interaction and remote control, requiring thorough validation of API request formatting, message classification, and delivery reliability. The command interpretation logic uses JSON parsing and keyword-based natural language understanding to distinguish between control commands, status requests, announcements, and AI queries. Visual feedback is provided through an onboard RGB LED, which indicates system states such as listening, processing, idle, and network connectivity.

On the hardware side, the ESP32-S3 N8R2 serves as the main processing unit, responsible for handling speech input, executing API communication, managing LED states, and transmitting commands to the remote device. The INMP441 I2S microphone enables high-quality audio capture, while the MAX98357A amplifier

delivers clear, real-time audio responses. The remote smart device uses an ESP32-WROOM board to manage relays controlling appliances such as fans and lamps while collecting environmental data through sensors like the DHT22 for temperature and humidity and the MQ2 for gas detection. These components undergo testing to ensure accurate sensing, responsive actuation, and stable wireless communication.

Additional hardware elements include relays, load drivers, and the RGB status LED, each tested for electrical reliability and synchronized system feedback. Together, the combined software hardware ecosystem undergoes a structured testing plan involving unit testing, integration testing, system testing, and performance evaluation.

This ensures that the assistant can reliably interpret voice and WhatsApp inputs, perform cloud-based AI processing, control room devices, handle alerts, and maintain stable communication even during fluctuating network conditions. The resulting system provides a robust, intelligent, and user-friendly voice assistant capable of operating effectively in practical environments such as classrooms, homes, or laboratories.

FUTURE WORK

Future enhancements to the AI Voice Assistant Using API can significantly broaden its capabilities, improve its intelligence, and expand its scope of applications. One major advancement lies in integrating advanced speech recognition models directly on the device using optimized edge-AI techniques.

This would reduce dependence on cloud services, enabling faster response times, improved privacy, and complete functionality in fully offline environments. Another promising direction is the

inclusion of a dedicated wake-word engine optimized for microcontrollers, ensuring highly accurate and low-power activation even in noisy surroundings.

The system can also evolve into a more immersive and context-aware assistant by incorporating machine learning-based intent prediction and adaptive behavior. This would allow the assistant to learn user habits, predict frequently used commands, and automate routine actions without explicit instructions. Further enhancements could include multi-language support, enabling the assistant to understand and respond in various regional languages, improving accessibility in diverse environments such as classrooms, homes, and public installations.

Additionally, expanding the smart environment ecosystem with multiple ESP32 nodes would allow the assistant to control an entire network of appliances, sensors, and environmental devices across different rooms or buildings. Features such as real-time data logging, energy-usage analytics, and automated safety alerts (e.g., gas leak, fire, or abnormal temperature spikes) could be integrated to improve safety and efficiency.

Another important avenue for future development is the integration of Whisper-based on-device STT, high-quality TTS engines, and multilingual AI models, enabling richer, more natural interactions. The system could also support screen-based output, such as a small display to show messages, AI responses, or sensor data. Beyond voice and messaging, incorporating gesture-based control, proximity sensing, or camera-based recognition could make the assistant more intuitive and responsive to its environment.

Overall, the future scope of this project is vast. By combining advancements in

embedded processing, edge AI, cloud intelligence, and IoT automation, the assistant has the potential to evolve into a highly adaptive, human-centric system capable of functioning as a personal companion, classroom automation tool, smart-home controller, or even an intelligent facility-management assistant in academic and commercial settings.

CONCLUSION

The AI Voice Assistant Using API successfully demonstrates how embedded systems, cloud intelligence, and smart automation can be integrated into a compact, efficient, and highly interactive solution. By leveraging the capabilities of the ESP32-S3, cloud-based APIs, and local wireless communication, the system provides seamless voice-controlled operation, intelligent response generation, and reliable device automation.

The assistant effectively interprets spoken commands, processes text-based instructions via WhatsApp, retrieves AI-generated information, and manages environmental sensing and appliance control through a dedicated smart device node.

The project highlights the potential of combining low-cost microcontrollers with powerful cloud APIs, enabling advanced AI features such as natural language understanding and conversational responses without requiring high-end hardware. The architecture also ensures resilience by supporting local communication through ESP-NOW, allowing device control even when internet connectivity is limited or unavailable.

The inclusion of RGB LED indicators, real-time sensing and automated alert generation further enhances the system's usability and practicality. Overall, this work provides a strong foundation for next-generation voice-controlled systems

in smart classrooms, homes, and workplaces. It demonstrates that intelligent assistants can be built using accessible hardware and modular software, offering both convenience and efficiency.

With future improvements such as offline speech processing, multi-language support, and advanced machine learning techniques, the proposed system can evolve into a more robust and fully autonomous AI assistant capable of delivering an even richer and more personalized user experience.

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